

Three-Terminal Transmission Line Fault Identification and Categorisation Using EMD Analysis Algorithm and Teager Energy Operator

S K Nazeer*‡, C. Mahalakshmi **, P. Kanta Rao***

* Research Scholar, Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram-608002.

**Associate Professor Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram-608002.

*** Professor, Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, S.R.K.R. Engineering College, Bhimavaram, India-534204.

‡ S K Nazeer, Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, S.R.K.R. Engineering College, Bhimavaram, India-534204

Abstract: Transmission line problems must be detected and repaired quickly to sustain power system operation. Empirical mode decomposition (EMD) with Teager energy operator (TEO) was utilized to determine the instantaneous energy of the initial intrinsic mode functions (IMFs) employed in fault identification and diagnostics to overcome these disruptions. We utilize EMD to deconstruct fault transients because it can extract time and frequency data concurrently. Transmission line voltages are decomposed into a finite and frequently small number of IMFs using EMD. Each IMF component has main eigenvalues. IMFs have unique effective component contents. Multiplying IMFs yields a fault index to detect different failure kinds. The recommended fault index threshold values are sent to the TEO for fault detection and classification. We found that the suggested method identifies and classifies power system failures.

Keywords- distance protection, fault classification, EMD, TEO.

I. INTRODUCTION

An integral aspect of every electrical grid is the transmission lines. Maintaining a steady supply of electricity for end users is the primary function of transmission lines. Faults that are not under human control happen as a result of natural calamities. Therefore, we can safeguard the transmission cables from various fault signals. In modern times, several approaches are employed to discover faults. Transmission lines with two terminals employ wavelet packet transform (WPT). There are four things it can do. There are a number of distinct types of defects, both temporary and permanent, and arc instant detection is one of them [1-3]. A voltage shift indicates a problem in the phasor measuring unit (PMU). Fault detection is a two-step process. Finding the fault location is the first step, and finding the corresponding index is the second. In the second step, the fault line and distance are accurately

detected. Large TL typically employ this technique. The excessively high fault resistance is an issue with this method [4].

Fault localization and classification are two other areas that make use of the ANN (Artificial Neural Network) approach. Back propagation is a technique used by ANN. Characteristic quantity classification makes use of it. In this examination of TL faults, the energy and coefficients, as well as the maximum and lowest values of the fault currents, are broken down. However, this approach yields accurate results, but it requires advanced computational abilities [5-8].

Characteristic quantities can be extracted using the Wavelet Transform (WT). The primary use of WT is the identification of transitory signal faults. Selecting the best mother wavelet is a challenge in WT. Different outputs can be produced by applying different compromised mother wavelets to the same signal. Among its many applications in image processing, WT is particularly well-suited for detecting voltage and current signals in the frequency and time domains. Since Fourier Transform is exclusively applied to the frequency domain, WT circumvents this limitation. Here, the signals are decomposed using low-frequency and high-frequency filters in order to get the coefficients. Failure detection then makes use of these signals [9-12].

Classification of faults and fault placement in TL are heavily reliant on WT with fuzzy logic combinations. Fuzzy logic is employed to extract features from WT, and WT with Multi-Resolution Analysis is utilized for fault arrangement [13-15]. For the purpose of finding power system network failures, the Hilbert Huang Transform is utilized in two components, the Hilbert Transform (HT) and the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) [16,17]. The use of rule-based decision trees (RBDTs) and Hilbert Huang Transforms (HHTs) to identify and categorize power system issues [18].

Weighing the benefits and drawbacks of the aforementioned approaches, we develop a new defect diagnostic system using EMD and TEO. Nonlinear and non-stationary signals can be sifted into simple and symmetric components using Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD). It decomposes the signal into IMFs, or Intrinsic Mode Functions. Therefore, the energy index is generated using the Teager Energy Operator (TEO) approach, and the same mode is also utilized to extract IMFs from EMD. Software such as MATLAB/SIMULINK is used to simulate the models. Various transient occurrences are simulated, including developing faults, close-in and far-distance faults, and faults with high resistance. The results section contains all of the stated findings.

The paper organization is as follows: Section II Test System Used for Study. Section III Proposed Methodology for Fault Detection. In Section IV the results for different cases are presented and finally Section V is conclusion section of the paper.

II. TEST SYSTEM USED FOR STUDY

The section provides a full discussion of the models used for study of the power system. The simulation research makes use of three terminal transmission system models. The distances covered by buses 1, 2, and 3's transmission lines (TMLs) are 100, 120, and 150 kilometers, respectively. Faults at the distant end, faults with high resistance, and faults near to the circuit's terminals are common and can cause protection issues. Therefore, a precise modeling line is required to carry out such a test.

The suggested method's response test and simulation analysis are carried out using the single line circuit for teed circuit illustrated in Fig. 1. On the MATLAB/SIMULINK 2020 platform, the system is simulated.

Fig.1. Three terminal circuit transmission line.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY FOR FAULT DETECTION

To identify and categorize faults on transmission lines, the suggested technique employs a two-step computational procedure. It all starts with an EMD analysis of the raw voltage data [16]–[18]. In order to get the energy index, the signal is first decomposed using several modes. Then, the most significant mode is recovered using Kurtosis analysis. The TEO is utilized in the line's fault analysis duty after being approximated from the appropriate mode. Below, you can find detailed descriptions of both ways.

A. Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD)

By use of a shifting process, the EMD method assists in decomposing a time domain signal $x(t)$ into a succession of independent moving fields (IMFs), where each IMF comprises a signal with a different range of frequencies and a different time scale. Identical to wavelet decomposition, signal decomposition involves building sub-bands according to the need to differentiate distinct components in the signal $x(t)$. The signal's highest frequency component, $x(t)$, is contained in the first IMF, which is called IMF1. The subsequent levels may be broken down in the same way, with the residual mode serving as the final mode. The EMD method is data driven as it does not employ a filtering procedure. At least one minimum and one maximum are required for the decomposition of any signal $x(t)$ into various IMFs to be successful. Here is how the shifting procedure can be carried out:

- First set the value $\varepsilon, c \leftarrow 1$ (k^{th} IMF)
- Then consider $j_{c-1}(t) \leftarrow x(t)$ (residual)
- After that extract the k^{th} IMF
- Update residual value: $j_c(t) \leftarrow j_{c-1}(t) - \text{IMF}_k(t)$.

The evaluated signal, which is a function of the total of all IMFs, is defined by the EMD algorithm, $(N_i(t))$ and residue, $(j(t))$, is represented as:

$$X(t) = \sum_k N_i(t) + j(t) \quad (1)$$

where, ' k ' represents the integrating IMF number

Due to the presence of high-frequency components produced by fault occurrences, the first decomposed mode via the EMD filter is utilized. Next, the TEO is estimated using the IMF1. The next section explains how TEO is processed for IMF1.

B. Teager Energy Operator (TEO). [19, 20]

Random signal energy may be measured in time domain by averaging the square of its amplitude. The square of a signal's Fourier transform helps assess its frequency domain spectral energy density. Parseval's theorem states that the energy of a signal's temporal and frequency domain representations are identical. The Parseval's relation (2) adds the energies of J samples, where $x(j)$ is the discrete time domain signal and $X(k)$ is its DFT.

$$\sum_{j=0}^{J-1} x[j]^2 = \frac{1}{J} \sum_{k=0}^{J-1} X[k]^2 \quad (2)$$

TEO calculates instantaneous energy based on signal amplitude and frequency. The TEO of a continuous time domain signal, $e(t)$, is found in (3), where $\dot{e}(t)$ and $\ddot{e}(t)$ denote the first and second derivatives, respectively. The TEO of a discrete time signal is computed using only three consecutive samples, as illustrated in (4), resulting in high time resolution.

$$\gamma [e(t)] = \dot{e}(t)^2 - e(t) \ddot{e}(t) \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma [e(n)] = e(n)^2 - e(n-1) e(n+1) \quad (4)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 transmission system architecture are simulated in MATLAB/SIMULINK and the algorithms are evaluated in MATLAB @2020. System line parameters used to evaluate the scheme are: $R_0 = 0.01687$ ohm/km, $R_1 = 0.025$, $L_0 = 3.8$ mH/km, $L_1 = 0.92$, $C_0 = 0.0073$ μ F/km, and $C_1 = 0.014$ μ F/km. A 400 kHz sample rate is used. System frequency is 50 Hz. The proposed method detects and classifies power system defects on a 400 kV transmission line by decomposing the voltages or currents at both ends.

We put the test system through its paces by simulating all kinds of errors. For six cycles, the voltage signals are recorded at both ends of the transmission line for 0.1 s (for 6 cycles). By converting the phase voltage signal to modal values of decomposition, its empirical mode decomposition (EMD) may be derived. Determined are the intrinsic mode functions at the decomposition level. Following the steps outlined below, multiply the intrinsic mode functions by 1. According to the research plan, this is called a defect index. Determine the maximum values of the fault indices and categorize the different fault kinds using the TEO.

A. Detection results.

This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of finding faults and section classification on three-terminal lines in restoring these lines to the network after a fault has occurred using data collected after the fact. This data is retrieved once the fault detection procedure is finished. So, to show how effective the VMD-TEO based method is, the article employs it to find problems fast.

i. BUS-1: Line to Ground Fault.

Line-to-ground (LG) faults are simulated at 10% of line length with an inception angle of 30° degrees and source-1 fault resistance of 50ohms. EMD is used to deconstruct the output modal value from bus-1 voltages. The first level of breakdown yields IMFs. The suggested fault index is derived using IMFs at the first decomposition level. In sequence, Fig. 2 (a), (b), (c), and (d) show bus-1 three-phase voltages, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition. IMFs have significant disruption components when they fail. Both bus-2 and bus-3 yield results, although at different levels.

Fig.2. Configuration settings on bus-1 at 10% of line length during LG failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1 (d) TEO-Fault index.

As seen in Fig. 2 (d), the fault index was computed on bus-1 during the creation event at 0.02166 seconds LG fault, which is at the close-end. We find that the fault index is initially set to zero before any faults occur. As a result, the suggested technique successfully detects LG faults in 0.02183 seconds. Therefore, the issue was identified within 0.17 milliseconds of the fault occurring.

ii. BUS-2: Double Line Fault.

The voltages recorded on bus-2 are decomposed to give the modal value of the output, which is further decomposed using EMD. IMFs are acquired at the first decomposition level after simulating a double line (LL) fault at 50% of the line length, 90° inception angle, and 100Ω fault resistance at source-2. At the first level of decomposition, IMFs are used to derive the proposed fault index. Fig. 3 (a), (b), (c), and (d) show the three phase voltages on bus-1, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition, in that order. At the time a failure occurs, it is noted that IMFs display substantial disturbance components. Both bus-1 and bus-3 provide findings that are quite similar but of somewhat different magnitudes.

Fig.3. Configuration settings on bus-2 at 50% of line length during LL failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1 (d) TEO-Fault index.

In Fig. 3 (d), we can see that the middle-end fault index was computed on bus-2 during the 0.025-second LL creation event. We find that the fault index is initially set to zero before any faults occur. And therefore, the suggested approach successfully detects LL faults in 0.0252 seconds. Therefore, the problem is identified within 0.2 milliseconds of the fault occurring.

iii. BUS-3: Double Line to Ground Fault

At 80% of the line length, with an inception angle of 120° and a fault resistance of 150Ω at source-3, a double line to ground (LLG) fault is modelled. The voltages recorded on bus-3 are decomposed to give the modal value of the output, which is further decomposed using EMD. At the first decomposition level, IMFs are acquired. At the first level of decomposition, IMFs are used to derive the proposed fault index. Fig. 4 (a), (b), (c), and (d) show the three phase voltages on bus-1, modal values, and IMF at the first level of decomposition, in that order. At the time a failure occurs, it is noted that IMFs display substantial disturbance components. On bus-1 and bus-2, we find comparable findings, but of somewhat different magnitudes.

Fig.4. Configuration settings on bus-3 at 80% of line length during LLG failure (a) three phase voltages (b) Modal voltage Signal (c) intrinsic mode function-1 (d) TEO-Fault index.

As seen in Fig. 4 (d), the fault index was computed on bus-3 during the 0.02667sec LLG fault occurrence. The fault is located at the far end. We find that the fault index is initially set to zero before any faults occur. As a result, the suggested approach successfully detects LLG faults in 0.02683 seconds. Consequently, the problem was recognized within 0.16 milliseconds of the fault occurrence.

B. Classification of Transmission Line Faults

Fig. 5. FSI values at all terminals for BCG-fault, (a) S1 at 40 kms, (b) S2 at 60 kms (c) S3 at 80 kms

Fig. 5 displays the efficacy of the suggested strategy in precisely identifying problematic sections. Transmission line fault categorization using TEO. To categorize the different kinds of defects that have been evaluated, threshold values of the fault index are utilized. By utilizing threshold values, the flaws have been individually distinguished from one another. The maximum values of the fault indices at the two ends of the transmission line were used to determine the threshold values.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this research is to examine EMD and TEO fault categorization and detection in power systems. The suggested fault index is calculated by multiplying the corresponding values of the IMFs at the first decomposition stages. At each end of the transmission line, this fault index is computed. Faults LG, LL, LLG, LLL, and LLLG have been examined. In the absence of a defect, the fault indices are zero, but they take on non-zero values when an error occurs. Different kinds of errors can be distinguished from one another by obtaining threshold values. To categorize the different kinds of errors, TEO is applied to the threshold values. There is no longer any need for zero sequence components according to the suggested approach. The results show that the suggested algorithm can successfully identify and categorize different kinds of power system failures.

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